

Thermodynamic Study of Exchange Reaction Between H-Resin and Montmorillonite-Clay

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Experimental results are presented for the changes of free energy, enthalpy and entropy pertaining to the exchange reaction between H-resin and montmorillonite clay containing exchangeable Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} , ions in condition simulating soil-plant root system. The exchange reaction has been carried out with different clay concentrations at two different temperatures. The selectivity co-efficients thus obtained have been utilised for the evaluation of free energy changes. The enthalpy changes are calculated from the observed temperature coefficient of selectivity and thence the entropy changes from the standard thermodynamic relations.

The values of free energy, enthalpy and entropy changes have been found to be positive. The difference in the heat of exchange reactions for the Cu and Ni-ions may be due to their difference in atomic weight, particle size and degree of hydration. The relatively large entropy change of the reaction of Ni-clay for the H^+ -ion in comparison with those of Cu-clay, is probably due to their difference in orientation and ion hydration on the clay surface.

THE importance of the thermodynamic study of the ion exchange reactions of clay are envisaged by different workers¹⁻¹⁸.

The aim of the present investigation is to obtain further information from thermodynamic approach, for the exchange reactions specially for those which simulates soil-plant root conditions. Many attempts have been made to study these exchange reactions by using artificial means. Of these, the method adopted by Brown and Albrecht¹⁹ and later on by Chatterjee²¹ is very fruitful. In the present investigation clays having exchangeable Nickel and Copper have been studied, at two different temperatures, under conditions simulating soil plant root relationship.

The selectivity co-efficients are calculated by the same procedure as reported in earlier paper^{22,23}.

The thermodynamic quantities ΔH , ΔG and ΔS are calculated by using standard thermodynamic relations. For the sake of simplicity all the reactants and products are assumed to be in their respective standard states so that ΔH , ΔG and ΔS may be

taken as standard thermodynamic functions viz., ΔH° , ΔG° and ΔS° respectively.

Experimental

The method of treatment of H-clay for the preparation of Ni and Cu-clays and of the resin for the exchange reaction was described by Nag and Chatterjee in earlier paper²². The exchange experiments between these clay-salts and H-resin were carried out at two different temperatures. The constancy in temperatures was maintained by wax-sealing and immersing the reaction vessels in constant temperature bath provided with cooling coils with an accuracy of $\pm 0.2^\circ$. The vessels were kept in that condition with occasional shaking till equilibrium was attained. The amount of cations replaced by the H^+ -ions of the resin was determined by following the same method as mentioned earlier²².

The selectivity co-efficients, $K_{\text{H}^+}^{\text{M}^{2+}}$ where M^{2+} represents Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} were used to calculate the thermodynamic functions (ΔG° , ΔH° , ΔS°) for the exchange reactions. The results are given in the following tables.

TABLE I.—REACTION BETWEEN H-RESIN AND CU-CLAY AT 10° AND AT 45°

Total $\text{Cu}^{2+} = 53 \text{ meq}/100 \text{ g dry clay}$

Amount of resin corresponding to	0.83% clay				2.19% clay				5.47% clay			
	10°		45°		10°		45°		10°		45°	
	Meq. of H^+ -ions replaced by Cu^{2+} -ions/100 g dry clay	Selectivity coefficient	Meq. of H^+ -ions replaced by Cu^{2+} -ions/100 g dry clay	Selectivity coefficient	Meq. of H^+ -ions replaced by Cu^{2+} -ions/100 g dry clay	Selectivity coefficient	Meq. of H^+ -ions replaced by Cu^{2+} -ions/100 g dry clay	Selectivity coefficient	Meq. of H^+ -ions replaced by Cu^{2+} -ions/100 g dry clay	Selectivity coefficient	Meq. of H^+ -ions replaced by Cu^{2+} -ions/100 g dry clay	Selectivity coefficient
0.5S	13.09	0.3123	15.70	0.8896	10.74	0.1180	12.63	0.2593	9.00	0.0541	10.90	0.1264
1.0S	25.32	0.7649	32.14	3.6550	20.18	0.2324	24.30	0.6068	9.17	0.0092	14.08	0.0474
1.5S	27.10	0.2800	36.01	1.4530	25.01	0.1882	27.12	0.2808	12.13	0.0096	15.17	0.0223
2.0S	28.01	0.1445	36.01	0.5620	26.64	0.1140	30.30	0.2138	15.28	0.0115	18.23	0.0226

TABLE 2—REACTION BETWEEN H-RESIN AND CU CLAY AT 10° AND AT 45°

Free energy, entropy and enthalpy changes

Amount of resin corresponding to	0.83% clay				2.19% clay				5.47% clay					
	10°		45°		10°		45°		10°		45°			
	ΔG° K cal/mole	ΔS° e.u./mole	ΔG° K cal/mole	ΔS° e.u./mole	ΔG° K cal/mole	ΔS° e.u./mole	ΔH° K cal/mole	ΔG° K cal/mole	ΔS° e.u./mole	ΔG° K cal/mole	ΔS° e.u./mole	ΔH° K cal/mole		
0.5S	+0.6588	+16.69	+0.0744	+16.69	+1.2100	+10.03	+0.8584	+10.03	+4.049	+1.648	+9.600	+1.316	+9.58	+4.365
1.0S	+0.1516	+27.99	-0.8243	+27.91	+0.8260	+14.52	+0.3177	+14.52	+4.937	+2.656	+20.47	+1.941	+20.46	+8.450
1.5S	+0.7204	+27.37	-0.2377	+27.37	+0.9454	+3.89	+0.8079	+3.899	+2.048	+2.611	+6.046	+2.418	+5.98	+4.322
2.0S	+1.095	+20.30	+0.3665	+20.81	+1.2290	+7.084	+0.9813	+7.079	+3.234	+2.527	+3.357	+2.410	+3.355	+3.477

TABLE 4—REACTION BETWEEN H-RESIN AND NI-CLAY AT 10° AND AT 42°

Free energy, entropy and enthalpy changes

Amount of resin corresponding to	0.925% clay				2.06% clay				6.43% clay					
	10°		42°		10°		42°		10°		42°			
	ΔG° K cal/mole	ΔS° e.u./mole	ΔG° K cal/mole	ΔS° e.u./mole	ΔG° K cal/mole	ΔS° e.u./mole	ΔH° K cal/mole	ΔG° K cal/mole	ΔS° e.u./mole	ΔG° K cal/mole	ΔS° e.u./mole	ΔH° K cal/mole		
0.5S	+0.763	+25.02	-0.0379	+25.04	+1.572	+44.36	+0.1451	+44.39	+14.13	+2.143	+48.78	+2.5794	+48.80	+15.95
1.0S	+1.123	+11.68	+0.7485	+11.68	+2.073	+26.59	+1.223	+26.59	+9.598	+2.249	+32.97	+1.195	+32.97	+11.58
1.5S	+1.565	+27.62	+0.6816	+27.62	+2.496	+36.00	+1.344	+36.02	+12.69	+2.770	+33.04	+1.712	+33.04	+12.12
2.0S	+1.923	+33.41	+0.8553	+33.41	+2.767	+43.72	+1.368	+43.71	+15.14	+2.968	+40.50	+1.671	+40.51	+14.43

TABLE 3—REACTION BETWEEN H-RESIN AND NI-CLAY AT 10° AND AT 42°

 Total Ni²⁺ = 64.48 meq./100 g dry clay

Amount of resin corresponding to	0.925% clay				2.06% clay				6.43% clay			
	10°		42°		10°		42°		10°		42°	
	Meq. of H ⁺ -ions replaced by Ni ²⁺ -ions/100 g dry clay	Selectivity coefficient	Meq. of H ⁺ -ions replaced by Ni ²⁺ -ions/100 g dry clay	Selectivity coefficient	Meq. of H ⁺ -ions replaced by Ni ²⁺ -ions/100 g dry clay	Selectivity coefficient	Meq. of H ⁺ -ions replaced by Ni ²⁺ -ions/100 g dry clay	Selectivity coefficient	Meq. of H ⁺ -ions replaced by Ni ²⁺ -ions/100 g dry clay	Selectivity coefficient	Meq. of H ⁺ -ions replaced by Ni ²⁺ -ions/100 g dry clay	Selectivity coefficient
0.5S	15.37	0.2598	19.61	0.0620	11.34	0.0629	18.76	0.7945	8.85	0.0228	16.66	0.3986
1.0S	21.96	0.1377	25.94	0.3048	14.69	0.0257	22.16	0.1436	13.55	0.0188	22.39	0.1503
1.5S	23.86	0.0630	34.22	0.3390	15.73	0.0122	27.56	0.1185	13.78	0.0075	24.12	0.0660
2.0S	24.46	0.0335	38.22	0.2582	16.58	0.0075	32.42	0.1140	15.03	0.0053	29.16	0.0705

Discussion

The standard free energy change (ΔG°) for the exchange of both Cu²⁺ ions and Ni²⁺ ions for H⁺-ions of the resin in Cu and Ni-clay respectively are found to be positive in most of the cases^{9,17}. This shows that the ions like Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ are preferred to the clay surface to H⁺-ions, a fact which can easily be understood when we consider the process of nutrient uptake by plants, the plant roots always exchange H⁺-ions for the other cations present in soils. This value also increased with increasing clay concentration indicating that the rate of exchange reaction decreases as the clay concentration increases^{22,23}.

A somewhat irregular manner of variation of the free energy changes with the symmetry concentration of the resin used, may be attributed to the over simplification of the problem by taking into account the concentration and not the activity of the ions involved in calculating the selectivity coefficients of the exchange reactions.

The standard enthalpy changes (ΔH°) for the exchange reactions studied, are all positive showing that the reactions are accompanied by absorption of heat which is evident from the fact that the rate of exchange increases with the rise in temperature. The heat of exchange reactions (ΔH°) for the ions are different in magnitude which may be due to their difference in atomic weight, particle size, degree of hydration and polarizability¹³. The values for the Ni-clay system are somewhat higher than those of Cu-clay which may probably be regarded as a stronger affinity between the Ni²⁺ ion and the clay surface than that exists between Cu²⁺ ion and the clay surface¹⁵.

The standard entropy change (ΔS°) values are not only positive for both Ni and Cu-clay but they remain constant for the two temperatures at which the reactions are carried out. Moreover, the reaction of Ni-clay for H⁺-ion is accompanied by larger values of ΔS° is comparison with those of Cu-clay. This is probably due to the fact that Cu²⁺ ion is more orderly arranged on the clay surface

than Ni¹⁶. Assuming that exchange takes place from orderly arrangement of ions on the clay surface, larger amount of energy will be required for the exchange of Ni than Cu. This is in accordance with the fact that ΔH° values of Ni-clay exchange are higher than those of Cu-clay exchange.

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